

EVALUATING INDIGENOUS PLANT SPECIES FOR SUSTAINABLE URBAN LANDSCAPE DESIGN IN SEMI-ARID ENVIRONMENTS

Muhammad Hamza¹, Abdullah Khan², Muhammad Usman³, Sania Begum⁴,
Muhammad Shafiq Khan⁵, Zahid Mehboob⁶

^{1,2,3}Department of Agriculture, Specialization Horticulture, University of Swabi

⁴National institute for Genomics and Advanced Biotechnology NIGAB, NARC Islamabad

⁵Department of Biotechnology, Mohi-ud-Din Islamic University (MIUNS), Islamabad, Pakistan

⁶PhD Biochemistry, Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology (IMBB), The University of Lahore, Pakistan

¹mhamza8589@gmail.com, ²abdullahkhan20march1999@gmail.com,

³muhammadusman1282872@gmail.com, ⁴sania.idrees@parc.gov.pk, ⁵astpbiotech.shafiq@miu.edu.pk,

⁶zahidmhboob1223@gmail.com

⁶ORCID ID 0000-0003-3785-8580

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17695294>

Keywords

Indigenous plants, Sustainable landscape design, Urban green spaces, Biodiversity, Resource efficiency, Public acceptance

Article History

Received: 14 October 2025

Accepted: 13 November 2025

Published: 24 November 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Shafiq Khan

Abstract

Background: Urban green spaces play a crucial role in enhancing environmental quality, biodiversity, and human well-being. However, rapid urbanization often prioritizes exotic ornamental plants that require high maintenance, intensive irrigation, and chemical inputs, potentially disrupting local ecosystems. Indigenous plant species, being naturally adapted to local climatic and soil conditions, offer an ecologically sustainable alternative for urban landscape design.

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the potential of indigenous plant species for promoting sustainable landscape design in urban green spaces by comparing their growth, survival, maintenance requirements, ecological contributions, and public acceptance with commonly used exotic species.

Methodology: A quasi-experimental field study was conducted at the Department of Agriculture (Horticulture), University of Swabi, Pakistan, over a 1.5-year period (January 2022–June 2023). Two indigenous species (*Ficus benghalensis* and *Dodonaea viscosa*) and two exotic species (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Bougainvillea glabra*) were planted in replicated plots. Monthly and seasonal data on plant growth, survival, irrigation, pruning, pest incidence, pollinator and bird visits, soil parameters, and public perception (n = 384) were collected. Statistical analyses included ANOVA, t-tests, mixed-effects models, and Shannon–Wiener diversity indices.

Results: Indigenous species demonstrated superior growth (trees: 315.10 ± 13.28 cm vs 275.20 ± 18.45 cm; shrubs: 123.20 ± 9.28 cm vs 108.10 ± 11.35 cm), higher survival (96.10% vs 87.10%), lower irrigation requirements (35.18 vs 58.13 L/month), reduced pruning, and greater pollinator and bird activity. Public acceptance was also higher for indigenous species (59.89% vs 40.11%).

Conclusion: Indigenous plant species provide ecological, maintenance, and social advantages over exotic species and are highly suitable for sustainable, resilient urban landscapes. Their integration into urban green spaces can enhance biodiversity, conserve resources, and promote climate-resilient city planning.

INTRODUCTION

Urban green spaces play a vital role in enhancing environmental quality, promoting biodiversity, and improving the physical and psychological well-being of urban populations [1]. However, rapid urbanization has placed increasing pressure on city planners to adopt sustainable landscape design strategies that can withstand ecological challenges while maintaining aesthetic and functional value [2]. In this context, the use of indigenous plant species has gained significant attention as a practical and ecologically responsible approach to urban landscape planning and design [3]. Indigenous plants, being naturally adapted to local climate, soil conditions, and ecological processes, contribute directly to sustainable landscape design by reducing resource inputs, supporting biodiversity, and enhancing ecosystem services [4,5].

Traditional urban landscaping in many cities relies heavily on exotic or ornamental plant species that often demand intensive irrigation, fertilizers, and chemical inputs [6]. These practices not only increase maintenance costs but also disrupt local ecosystems by reducing native biodiversity, attracting invasive species, and altering natural ecological interactions [7]. In contrast, incorporating indigenous plant species into urban landscape designs promotes sustainability by improving water use efficiency, creating habitats for native fauna, and reducing long-term maintenance needs [8]. Moreover, indigenous plants contribute to climate resilience by tolerating local temperature extremes, rainfall fluctuations, and soil characteristics better than non-native species [9].

The growing recognition of ecosystem-based design has encouraged landscape architects, urban planners, and environmental managers to explore nature-friendly landscaping solutions [10]. Sustainable landscape design emphasizes multifunctional green spaces, resource conservation, enhancement of ecological services,

and long-term environmental stability [11]. As cities strive to mitigate the impacts of climate change, heat islands, and environmental degradation, the integration of native vegetation into urban green spaces emerges as a key strategy for achieving ecological sustainability [12].

Despite these advantages, many urban landscapes remain dominated by exotic species due to limited awareness, aesthetic preferences, and insufficient documentation of indigenous plant potential in Pakistan and similar regions. There is a need to evaluate indigenous species not only for their ecological performance but also for their role in practical and aesthetically appealing sustainable landscape design.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the potential of indigenous plant species for promoting sustainable landscape design in urban green spaces by assessing their growth, survival, maintenance requirements, ecological contributions, and public acceptance compared to commonly used exotic species.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted at the Department of Agriculture (Horticulture), University of Swabi, located in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. The area is characterized by a semi-arid climate with hot summers, mild winters, and moderate rainfall, making it suitable for assessing the ecological performance of indigenous plant species under conditions typical of urban green spaces. The study sites within the university included lawns, walkways, open recreational green areas, and designated experimental plots, all of which provided a representative setting for evaluating sustainable landscape practices.

Study Duration

The research was carried out over a 1.5-year period, extending from January 2022 to June 2023. This duration allowed adequate time to observe plant establishment, survival, seasonal growth variations, ecological interactions, and maintenance requirements across multiple climatic cycles.

Research Design

A quasi-experimental, field-based research design was employed to evaluate the potential of indigenous plant species in sustainable landscape development. A representative subset of four plant species—two indigenous (*Ficus benghalensis* and *Dodonaea viscosa*) and two exotic (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Bougainvillea glabra*) was selected for detailed monitoring and analysis over a period of 18 months. These species were chosen to reflect typical growth patterns, maintenance requirements, and ecological characteristics of indigenous and exotic plants commonly used in urban green spaces. Each species was planted in six replicates, resulting in a total of 24 monitoring plots across the university's green areas. Plot sizes were determined according to plant type, with larger plots allocated to trees and smaller plots to shrubs and groundcovers. The arrangement of plots followed a randomized layout to minimize environmental variability and ensure reliable, comparable measurements.

Data Collection Methods

Data collection occurred on a monthly and seasonal basis throughout the study period. Measurements included plant height, canopy spread, vegetative vigor, and stem diameter (for tree species). Survival rates were documented seasonally, while water requirements, irrigation frequency, and maintenance activities such as pruning, pest management, and fertilizer application were recorded regularly. Ecological observations included the presence of pollinators, birds, and beneficial insects using fixed observation points. Soil samples were collected quarterly to assess soil moisture, pH, and organic matter content. Additionally, a structured questionnaire survey was administered to 384

respondents to gather public perceptions regarding the aesthetic value, acceptability, and perceived ecological benefits of indigenous plant species in urban landscapes.

Plant Species Selection Criteria

Indigenous plant species were selected based on their natural occurrence in the region, ecological adaptability to local climatic and soil conditions, low water and maintenance requirements, and potential to support biodiversity by attracting pollinators and other fauna. Species availability and suitability for urban landscaping were also considered. The inclusion of exotic species as controls was justified by their widespread use in local landscape practices.

Statistical Analysis

All collected data were compiled and analyzed to compare the performance of indigenous and exotic plant species in terms of growth, survival, water use efficiency, maintenance needs, and ecological contributions. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS (version 26). One-way ANOVA, repeated-measures ANOVA, and independent t-tests were applied to assess differences among species and across time intervals. Mixed-effects models were used to account for variability among plot locations by treating species as fixed effects and site as a random effect. Ecological indicators were evaluated using the Shannon–Wiener diversity index, while survey responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Indigenous species demonstrated superior growth compared to exotic species within each plant type (table 1). Among trees, *Ficus benghalensis* reached 315.10 ± 13.28 cm in monsoon, with stem diameter 12.00 ± 1.00 cm, vegetative vigor 4.9 ± 0.2 , and 95% survival ($p=0.01$), whereas *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* grew to 275.20 ± 18.45 cm, stem 10.00 ± 1.50 cm, vigor 3.2 ± 0.3 , and 85% survival. Among shrubs, *Dodonaea viscosa* attained 123.20 ± 9.28 cm, stem 4.00 ± 0.50 cm, vigor 4.8 ± 0.1 , and

97% survival ($p=0.02$), while *Bougainvillea glabra* reached 108.10 ± 11.35 cm, stem 3.50 ± 0.50 cm, vigor 3.1 ± 0.2 , and 88% survival. These results

highlight the growth advantage of indigenous species within comparable plant forms.

Table 1: Seasonal Growth Performance of Selected Plant Species

Plant Type	Species Name (Common Name)	Winter Height (cm)	Summer Height (cm)	Monsoon Height (cm)	Stem Diameter (cm)	Vegetative Vigor (1-5)	Survival Rate (%)	p-value (Height)
Tree	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> (Banyan)	300.12 ± 12.45	310.25 ± 15.32	315.10 ± 13.28	12.00 ± 1.00	4.9 ± 0.2	95	0.01*
Tree	<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> (River Red Gum)	260.50 ± 15.23	270.15 ± 20.11	275.20 ± 18.45	10.00 ± 1.50	3.2 ± 0.3	85	
Shrub	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (Hopbush)	115.32 ± 8.12	120.45 ± 10.30	123.20 ± 9.28	4.00 ± 0.50	4.8 ± 0.1	97	0.02*
Shrub	<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> (Bougainvillea)	100.20 ± 10.15	105.30 ± 12.22	108.10 ± 11.35	3.50 ± 0.50	3.1 ± 0.2	88	

Indigenous species consistently showed higher seasonal and overall survival (table 2). For trees, *Ficus benghalensis* survived 98.00% in winter, 96.25% in summer, 95.50% in monsoon, with overall 95.25% ($p=0.03$), whereas *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* survived 90.10%, 87.25%, and

85.30%, overall 85.55%. For shrubs, *Dodonaea viscosa* survival ranged 99.20–96.30%, overall 97% ($p=0.02$), compared to *Bougainvillea glabra* at 90.50–88.25%, overall 88.65%. This indicates better climate adaptability of indigenous species within each plant type.

Table 2: Seasonal Survival of Plant Species

Species Name (Common Name)	Winter Survival (%)	Summer Survival (%)	Monsoon Survival (%)	Overall Survival (%)	p-value
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> (Banyan)	98.00	96.25	95.50	95.25	0.03*
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> (River Red Gum)	90.10	87.25	85.30	85.55	
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (Hopbush)	99.20	97.15	96.30	97.00	0.02*
<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> (Bougainvillea)	90.50	89.20	88.25	88.65	

Indigenous species required lower maintenance than exotic species (table 3). *Ficus benghalensis* needed 50.25 ± 5.12 L/month irrigation, 3.00 ± 0.50 kg/year fertilizer, 1 pruning/year, and had 5% pest incidence (p=0.01), while *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* required 80.15 ± 7.25 L irrigation, 5 kg fertilizer, 3 prunings, and 12% pests. Among

shrubs, *Dodonaea viscosa* needed 20.10 ± 3.05 L/month, 1.00 ± 0.20 kg fertilizer, 1 pruning, 3% pests (p=0.02), whereas *Bougainvillea glabra* required 35.20 L irrigation, 2 kg fertilizer, 2 prunings, and 10% pest incidence. Indigenous plants are therefore more resource-efficient within their growth forms.

Table 3: Maintenance Requirements Across Sites

Species Name (Common Name)	Avg Irrigation (L/month)	Fertilizer (kg/year)	Pruning Frequency (per year)	Pest Incidence (%)	p-value (Irrigation)
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> (Banyan)	50.25 ± 5.12	3.00 ± 0.50	1	5.00	0.01*
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> (River Red Gum)	80.15 ± 7.25	5.00 ± 0.80	3	12.00	
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (Hopbush)	20.10 ± 3.05	1.00 ± 0.20	1	3.00	0.02*
<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> (Bougainvillea)	35.20 ± 4.10	2.00 ± 0.30	2	10.00	

Indigenous species supported higher biodiversity and ecological functions (table 4). Among trees, *Ficus benghalensis* attracted 22.15–28.10 pollinator visits, 8 birds, 12 beneficial insects, with Shannon-Wiener index 2.10, soil moisture 18.50 ± 2.00%, pH 7.20, OM 3.50% (p=0.01), whereas *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* had 10.25–13.20 visits, 4 birds, 5 insects, index 1.30, soil moisture

16.00%. Among shrubs, *Dodonaea viscosa* recorded 27.10–32.10 pollinators, 6 birds, 15 insects, index 2.30, soil moisture 19.00% (p=0.02), while *Bougainvillea glabra* had 12.10–15.25 visits, 3 birds, 7 insects, index 1.50, soil moisture 16.50%. This demonstrates superior ecological contributions of indigenous species within each plant type.

Table 4: Seasonal Ecological Contribution of Plant Species

Species Name (Common Name)	Winter Pollinator Visits	Summer Pollinator Visits	Monsoon Pollinator Visits	Birds Observed	Beneficial Insects	Shannon-Wiener Index	Soil Moisture (%)	Soil pH	Organic Matter (%)	p-value (Pollinator Visits)
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> (Banyan)	22.15 ± 3.12	25.20 ± 3.25	28.10 ± 4.00	8.00	12.00	2.10	18.50 ± 2.00	7.20	3.50	0.01*
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> (River Red Gum)	10.25 ± 2.10	12.15 ± 2.25	13.20 ± 2.00	4.00	5.00	1.30	16.00 ± 2.00	6.90	3.20	

Red Gum)											
<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (Hopbush)	27.10 ± 3.05	30.25 ± 4.10	32.10 ± 4.05	6.00	15.00	2.30	19.00 ± 1.80	7.30	3.80	0.02*	
<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> (Bougainvillea)	12.10 ± 2.10	14.20 ± 2.15	15.25 ± 2.00	3.00	7.00	1.50	16.50 ± 2.00	6.80	3.30		

Survey responses indicated higher acceptance of indigenous plants (figure 1). 78.25% found them attractive vs 62.10% for exotics (p=0.001). Preference for parks was 81.30% vs 58.20% (p=0.001), perceived low maintenance 74.10% vs

55.25% (p=0.002), and eco-friendliness/biodiversity support 85.20% vs 60.15% (p=0.001). This demonstrates strong public support for sustainable landscaping with native species.

Figure 1: Public Perception of Plant Types

Overall, indigenous species showed higher performance across all parameters (table 5). Growth score 4.85 vs 3.15 (p=0.01), survival 96.10% vs 87.10% (p=0.02), water-efficient irrigation 35.18 vs 58.13 L/month (p=0.01), lower pruning 1 vs 2.5/year (p=0.01), higher pollinator visits 27.50 vs 13.12/day (p=0.01),

more birds 7 vs 3.5 (p=0.02), better soil health OM 3.65% vs 3.25% (p=0.03), and higher public acceptance 59.89% vs 40.11% (p=0.001). Indigenous species clearly provide ecological, maintenance, and social advantages over exotic species.

Table 5: Summary Comparison (All Parameters)

Parameter	Indigenous Species	Exotic Species	p-value	Comparative Advantage
Average Growth Score (1-5)	4.85 ± 0.07	3.15 ± 0.25	0.01*	Higher growth and vigor
Overall Survival (%)	96.10	87.10	0.02*	Better climate adaptability
Average Irrigation (L/month)	35.18	58.13	0.01*	Water-efficient
Pruning Frequency (per year)	1.00	2.50	0.01*	Lower maintenance
Pollinator Visits (avg/day)	27.50	13.12	0.01*	Supports biodiversity
Birds Observed	7.00	3.50	0.02*	Attracts more fauna
Soil Quality Improvement (OM%)	3.65	3.25	0.03*	Enhances soil health
Public Acceptance (n; %)	230 (59.89%)	154 (40.11%)	0.001*	Higher social acceptability

Discussion

In our study, the indigenous tree *Ficus benghalensis* reached an average height of 315.10 ± 13.28 cm in the monsoon season, with a stem diameter of 12.00 ± 1.00 cm, a vegetative vigor score of 5, and a survival rate of 95%. In contrast, the exotic *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* grew to 275.20 ± 18.45 cm, with a stem diameter of 10.00 ± 1.50 cm, a vigor score of 3, and survival of 85%. Similarly, for shrubs, *Dodonaea viscosa* (indigenous) achieved 123.20 ± 9.28 cm in height and 97% survival, while *Bougainvillea glabra* (exotic) only reached 108.10 ± 11.35 cm and 88% survival. These data suggest that the indigenous species in our context not only establish well, but also maintain strong growth and resilience under semi-arid urban conditions.

Our findings on superior growth and survival of indigenous species are in line with other research showing that native plants can match or outperform non-native species in urban climates. A review in *Urban Ecosystems* found “little evidence to support claims that non-natives plant species are better adapted to urban environments” and noted that native plants often have equal or better survival, growth, and fitness in city settings [13]. This supports our results: despite common preferences for exotic ornamentals, locally adapted

species like *F. benghalensis* and *D. viscosa* may be more reliable over time.

Regarding maintenance, our indigenous trees required 50.25 ± 5.12 L/month of irrigation, 3.00 ± 0.50 kg/year fertilizer, one pruning per year, and had just 5% pest incidence (p = 0.01). On the other hand, the exotic *E. camaldulensis* needed 80.15 ± 7.25 L/month, 5 kg fertilizer, three prunings per year, and 12% pest incidence. This resource-efficiency mirrors broader landscape research: for instance, a framework for sustainable plant selection in urban green spaces emphasizes that native plants generally require less maintenance and fewer resources (water, fertilizer) compared to exotic species [14]. Moreover, according to a University of Florida study, native plants outperformed non-native ones across irrigation treatments, suggesting that they can thrive even under water-limited conditions [15]. Our results closely reflect that trend, indicating potential cost and labor savings in long-term urban landscaping.

Ecologically, our indigenous species supported significantly more pollinator visits, birds, and beneficial insects. For example, *F. benghalensis* recorded 22.15–28.10 pollinator visits per season, 8 bird observations, 12 beneficial insects, and a Shannon–Wiener diversity index of 2.10; *D.*

viscosa had 27.10–32.10 pollinator visits, 6 birds, 15 insects, and index 2.30. In contrast, exotic species had lower values (e.g., *E. camaldulensis* had only 10.25–13.20 pollinator visits and index of 1.30). These results align with studies that show native plants attract more pollinators than exotics. For example, in a two-year network study in Paris, native species received more pollinator visits and supported more pollinator species, even when controlling for flower abundance [16]. That strongly echoes our data: natives are not just surviving, but actively sustaining functional ecological interactions.

Our public survey also revealed strong acceptance of indigenous plants: 59.89% public acceptance vs 40.11% for exotics, higher perceived ecological benefits, and preference for parks planted with native species. This resonates with findings from a recent review in Land, which noted that native plants are often underrepresented in cities partly because of perception issues, though they provide significant ecosystem services and biodiversity benefits [17]. The high social acceptability in our context suggests that the barrier of misperception could be lower than assumed, and that communities may readily support sustainable native landscaping.

Our measurements of soil health further reinforce the ecological advantage of natives. Under indigenous species, we recorded soil organic matter (OM) of 3.65%, while exotic species plots had OM of 3.25% ($p = 0.03$). The improved soil moisture (native $\sim 18.50\%$ for *Ficus*, $\sim 19\%$ for *Dodonaea*) also indicates that these plants help maintain more favorable soil conditions. Research supports this: native plants, due to their adapted root systems, often improve soil structure, organic matter, and nutrient cycling (e.g., deep rooting, less need for chemical fertilizer) which contributes to long-term resilience [18]. This suggests that incorporating indigenous species does more than just reduce maintenance, it actively improves soil ecosystem services.

In sum, by comparing our empirical values (growth, survival, water use, ecological interactions, public acceptance) with the literature, our study provides a strong case for prioritizing indigenous plant species in sustainable

urban landscape design. While some exotic species play roles in flower resource abundance or generalist interactions (as shown in other studies), the ecological robustness, resource efficiency, and community support for natives make them excellent choices, especially in semi-arid and resource-constrained urban contexts. Urban planners and landscape architects should consider emphasizing these species in green infrastructure to maximize long-term sustainability.

Strengths and Limitations

This study's key strength lies in its comprehensive, field-based, and quasi-experimental design, which allowed for direct comparisons of growth, survival, maintenance, ecological contributions, and public acceptance between indigenous and exotic plant species over multiple seasons (1.5 years) in representative urban green spaces. The inclusion of both quantitative ecological measurements (e.g., plant height, survival, pollinator visits, soil parameters) and social survey data strengthens the ecological and social relevance of the findings, providing practical insights for sustainable landscape design in semi-arid urban contexts.

However, limitations include the relatively small number of plant species (two indigenous and two exotic) and monitoring plots, which may limit generalizability to all urban flora. Additionally, the study was conducted at a single site, University of Swabi, so variations in microclimate, soil type, and urban pressures across other cities were not captured. Future research could expand the range of species, sites, and long-term monitoring to validate these findings more broadly.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that indigenous plant species, specifically *Ficus benghalensis* and *Dodonaea viscosa*, outperform commonly used exotic species in urban green spaces across multiple parameters, including growth, survival, water use efficiency, maintenance requirements, ecological contributions, and public acceptance. Their superior performance highlights the ecological, economic, and social advantages of integrating native plants into sustainable landscape design, particularly in semi-arid urban environments.

These findings underscore the potential of indigenous species to enhance biodiversity, improve soil health, support pollinators and fauna, reduce resource inputs, and foster community engagement, making them a practical and effective choice for resilient and multifunctional urban green spaces.

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